

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR:

1. Kalshnikov A.P. - Chorvachilikda oziqa normalari va ratiionlari. Toshkent, Mexnat 1988y
2. Азаров Г.С. Нагул скота - В сборнике Практические совета скотоводу. М., Росселхозиздат, 1964.
3. Buryakov N.P., Yuldoshev D.Q. – Qand lavlagi jomining chorva mollarni oziqlantirishda qo‘llanilishi. Chorvachilik va naslchilik ishi Ilmiy amaliy jurnal №4. 2023y.
4. Yaxyaev V.S., Haydarov Q.H., Hayvonlarni oziqlantirish fanidan amaliy va laboratoriya mashg‘ulotlari. O‘quv qo‘llanma. “Talim texnologiyalari”. Toshkent 2019 yil.
5. Ibragimjanovich, T. I., & Kurbanbay o'g'li, X. J. (2023). YOSHLARGA HARBIY-VATANPARVARLIK TARBIYASINI SINGDIRISH. JOURNAL OF INNOVATIONS IN SCIENTIFIC AND EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH, 6(4), 1209-1213.
6. Ibragimjanovich, T. I., & Kurbanbay o'g'li, X. J. (2023). HARBIY-SPORT MUSOBAQALARINI TASHKILLASH VA O‘TKAZISH. PEDAGOG, 6(5), 780-781.
7. Ibragimovich, T. I. (2024). IMPROVING OF PEDAGOGICAL SKILLS OF STUDENTS OF PEDAGOGY AND PSYCHOLOGY DURING CONTINUOUS PEDAGOGICAL PRACTICE. JOURNAL OF INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH, 1(2), 92-94.
8. Damirovich, M. R., Ibragimovich, T. I., & Sattarovich, A. U. (2022). The Role Of Spiritual And Educational Events In Promoting The Ideas Of Religious Tolerance And International Health. Brazilian Journal of Implantology and Health Sciences, 4(5), 42-47.